

MED-GOLD

CLIMATE SERVICES

MED-GOLD DASHBOARD

GRANODURO.NET

MED-GOLD CASAS PBDM

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant agreement No. 776467

Developing climate services for European agriculture and food systems

www.med-gold.eu
@medgold_h2020
med-gold.project@enea.it

MED-GOLD ICT PLATFORM

CLIMATE SERVICES FOR THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR

Crystallizing a wealth of scientific and technological knowledge, the platform is a new versatile tool that integrates and harmonizes all the resources needed to build and run cutting-edge climate services, specifically designed for the widest range of end users in the agri-food sector.

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DIFFERENT USERS WITH MANY DIFFERENT NEEDS

DIFFERENT DATA AND RESOURCES

Climate predictions
Weather Data
Pest Databases
Biological models

Is there a tool for me?
Can I trust it?

IN A DIVERSE, NON-INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGICAL LANDSCAPE

MED-GOLD ADDED VALUE

CO-DEVELOPMENT WITH USERS

THE INFO PROVIDED IS

- TRUSTWORTHY
- UPDATED
- SPECIFICALLY TAILORED FOR THE USERS' SECTOR

FLEXIBLE
EFFICIENT
SCALABLE
REPLICABLE
EXPANDABLE
WITH NEW APPLICATIONS

INTEGRATION IN A SINGLE CENTRALIZED INFRASTRUCTURE WHERE ALL RESOURCES AND TOOLS ARE HARMONIZED AND WORK TOGETHER

CLIMATE SERVICES ARE CONNECTED / BUILT UPON THE PLATFORM

PROVIDING ACCESS TO DIFFERENT OUTPUTS, RESPONDING TO THE NEEDS OF A WIDE RANGE OF USERS

INFORMED DECISIONS BENEFITS

MED-GOLD DASHBOARD

CLIMATE SERVICES FOR THE GRAPE AND WINE SECTOR

A brand new service, providing reliable, up-to-date and tailored information to support the decision-making process of agronomists and enologists.

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CO-DEVELOPMENT WITH USERS

INTEGRATION IN MED-GOLD ICT PLATFORM

DATA AND RESOURCES

ADDED VALUE FOR THE USERS

KNOWLEDGE

Probable climate conditions in a month/ the next season/ end of century

Probability of climatic extremes for the future

Threats risk – diseases, pests, crop loss... based on climate predictions

Level of uncertainty of the predictions

BENEFITS

Seasonal resources optimization and best field operations timing

Identification of climate drivers of grape quality, wine type, business profitability

Informed planning for structural changes - site move, variety / wine type change, business model change

Awareness of predictions reliability for better decision making

FEATURES

Unique, brand new service

Short term, seasonal, and up to 30 years climate predictions

Unprecedented spatial resolution: 1 to 30 km

Reconstruction of present and past climate

Link to Copernicus Climate Data Store

MED-GOLD DASHBOARD

SIMPLE AND INTUITIVE INTERFACE

Maps

Charts

Data files

OUTPUTS

Historical climate data

Climate predictions: temperature, precipitations

Bioclimatic indicators

Risk indexes

Uncertainty estimates

Geographical distribution evaluation

MED-GOLD CASAS PBDM

PHYSIOLOGICALLY-BASED DEMOGRAPHIC MODELLING FOR OLIVE AND COFFEE

Research tool that models weather-driven biological processes for agroecosystem analysis. The original PBDM software was integrated in the MED-GOLD ICT Platform to greatly expand its usability and improve its functionalities.

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CO-DEVELOPMENT WITH USERS

INTEGRATION IN MED-GOLD ICT PLATFORM

DATA AND RESOURCES

ADDED VALUE FOR THE USERS

KNOWLEDGE

System thinking:

Deconstruction of complex system dynamics - Bio/climate/economy

Management-relevant understanding of complex ecosystem problems

BENEFITS

Improved regional crop management strategy

Resource optimization

Solutions for ecosystem problems (e.g. invasive pests)

Increased resilience to climate change

FEATURES

More flexible and scalable

More users/data/regions

Extensible to different crops and species

Short/mid/long term predictions

Link to Copernicus Climate Data Store

Independent of operating system

MED-GOLD CASAS PBDM

OUTPUTS

Pests number dynamics

Crop management recommendations

Rank of key production factors

Spatial / temporal statistics of risk changes

Maps of climate risk

Impact factors on crop

API

Maps

Charts

Tables

CO-DEVELOPMENT WITH USERS

CONNECTION TO MED-GOLD ICT PLATFORM

DATA AND RESOURCES

ADDED VALUE FOR THE USERS

SUPPORTED DECISIONS

BENEFITS

SHORT TERM OUTPUTS

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NEW OUTPUTS AT SEASONAL - UP TO 6 MONTHS - SCALE

SIMPLE AND INTUITIVE INTERFACE

TURNING CLIMATE-RELATED INFORMATION INTO ADDED VALUE FOR TRADITIONAL MEDITERRANEAN GRAPE, OLIVE AND DURUM WHEAT FOOD SYSTEMS

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Climate services for the agrifood sector will contribute to make European agriculture and food systems more resilient, sustainable and efficient in the face of climate change.

MED-GOLD has co-developed climate services with users, employing state of the art climate data, either building on existing tools with a high reputation in the respective sectors or creating new tools from scratch.

MED-GOLD ICT PLATFORM

The services rest on the MED-GOLD ICT platform, which is now at an advanced development level and can be replicated over wider geographical areas and in other sectors.

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The platform, and the services it enables, support the European Green Deal and the Common Agricultural Policy in ensuring that a sustainable and resilient agriculture will remain at the heart of Europe for generations to come.